

Complexes of Antimony Halides with Sulphonium Halides.

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In course of a recent investigation (Ray and Adhikari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 297) the exact nature of the reaction between mercuric iodide, alkyl sulphide (or polysulphide) and alkyl iodide has been clearly interpreted. It has been shown that alkyl sulphide and alkyl iodide interact to form sulphonium iodide which then combines with mercuric iodide to form compounds of the type of $[R_3S]_2HgI_4$ and $[R_3S]HgI_3$ analogous to the complex compounds K_2HgI_4 and $KHgI_3$. In the case of the alkyl polysulphides the extra sulphur atoms are split off and a sulphonium iodide is formed which then combines with mercuric iodide. Consequently the same compound is obtained starting with a sulphide or the corresponding polysulphide. That these compounds are really complexes of the type K_2HgI_4 and $KHgI_3$ is borne out by their general chemical behaviour and also by conductivity data.

This led the authors to investigate whether halides of any other metal, which do not belong to the mercury group, react in a similar way with alkyl sulphides and alkyl halides. In the course of the present work, the reaction between antimony halides, alkyl sulphides and alkyl halides, has been studied. Antimony was chosen because of its feeble electropositive character so that it may readily function as a central atom in a complex compound. Moreover compounds of the type $SbX_3 \cdot MX$ or $SbX_3 \cdot 3MX$ ($X = \text{halogen}$, $M = \text{alkali metal or ammonium}$) are quite well-known and are usually represented as $M[SbX_4]$ and $M_3[SbX_6]$. As a result the following compounds have been prepared and studied:—

The same compounds are obtained if we start with antimony halides and the corresponding sulphonium halide.

It has also been noticed that a sulphur atom is split off when a disulphide is substituted for the corresponding monosulphide resulting in the formation of an identical compound. All of these are coloured crystalline compounds, rather sparingly soluble in acetone, except the compound $[\text{Et}_3\text{S}]\text{SbBr}_4$ which freely dissolves, and is practically insoluble in other organic solvents. They are however decomposed by an excess of water, oxyhalides being precipitated.

Constitution.—These are undoubtedly complex compounds, although not of pronounced stability, of the type MSbI_4 or rather $[\text{SbI}_4]\text{M}$ according to Werner's method of formulation ionising in concentrated solution into the ions, SbI_4^- and M^+ . A solution of these compounds in acetone is coloured and on adding water gradually the colour disappears. An oxyhalide is precipitated only when sufficient water is added after the colour is fully discharged. The disappearance of colour is obviously due to the collapse of the complex. The values obtained for molecular conductivity at varying dilutions indicate that the compound dissociates into two ions at lower dilution although at higher dilutions the conductivity increases, presumably due to the breaking down of the complex. The complex nature of the series of compounds is also indicated by the fact that identical compound is obtained when either (i) SbI_3 is treated with excess of Et_3SBr or (ii) SbBr_3 is treated with excess of Et_3SI . If these were mere additive compounds, we would have expected two different compounds namely (i) $\text{SbI}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_3\text{SBr}$ and (ii) $\text{SbBr}_3 \cdot 3\text{Et}_3\text{SI}$. The identity of these two compounds, as indicated by their chemical and physical properties and also melting point, can only be satisfactorily explained by assuming that a complex compound of the type $[\text{Et}_3\text{S}]_3[\text{SbI}_3\text{Br}_3]$ is formed. It has been shown previously (Atkinson, *Chem. News*, 1883, 47, 175; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 43, 291) that the compounds $3\text{KBr} \cdot \text{SbCl}_3$ and $3\text{KCl} \cdot \text{SbBr}_3$ are also identical and hence has been represented as $\text{K}_3[\text{SbCl}_3\text{Br}_3]$.

The constitution of the other compounds of the series should therefore be represented as of the type $[\text{Et}_3\text{S}]\text{SbX}_4$ (X = halogen).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $[\text{Et}_3\text{S}]\text{SbI}_4$.—Antimony tri-iodide, ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide in molecular proportions are gently warmed together

on a water-bath under reflux. A mass of reddish-yellow powder is obtained which is separated and is purified by crystallisation from acetone. The compound is rather sparingly soluble and hence to bring it into solution, treatment with a large volume of boiling acetone is necessary. The bulk of the acetone is then removed by distilling gently from the water-bath. Crystals separate as the acetone is distilled off and on cooling further crystallisation occurs.

It is a red, glistening crystalline substance, m.p. 169° , sparingly soluble in acetone and insoluble in other solvents. It is decomposed on adding an excess of water. (Found: Sb, 15.99, 16.23; I, 68.26, 68.36; C, 9.41. $(C_2H_5)_3SI \cdot SbI_3$ requires Sb, 16.26; I, 67.84; C, 9.61 per cent. Sulphur is found to be present qualitatively).

If SbI_3 , Et_2S_2 and ethyl iodide, in equimolecular proportions, are heated together for about 2 hours under reflux, the contents of the flask gradually turn tarry. The tarry mass dissolves in acetone and on the addition of ether, a reddish-yellow substance is precipitated. This is separated and crystallised from acetone in the same way as the above compound. This has the same melting point (169°) and physical and chemical properties as the above compound. (Found: Sb, 16.15 per cent.).

The same compound is also obtained by treating antimony tri-iodide with $(C_2H_5)_3SI$. The compound $SbI_3 \cdot 3Et_3SI$ however could not be obtained, as might be expected, on treating SbI_3 with an excess of Et_3SI .

Preparation of $[Me_3S]SbI_4$.—It was prepared exactly in the same way as $[Et_3S]SbI_4$ from antimony iodide, methyl iodide and dimethyl sulphide. It is a reddish-yellow compound, m.p. 194° . Its properties are very similar to those of $[Et_3S]SbI_4$. (Found: Sb, 17.16; I, 72.43. $[(CH_3)_3S]SbI_4$ requires Sb, 17.23; I, 71.87 per cent.).

Sulphur was found to be present qualitatively. The same compound results when SbI_3 is either heated with $(CH_3)_2S_2$ and CH_3I or with $(CH_3)_3SI$. The compound $SbI_3 \cdot 3[(CH_3)_3SI]$ could not be prepared.

Preparation of $[Et_3S]SbBr_4$.—Antimony tribromide, diethyl sulphide and ethyl bromide in equimolecular proportion were heated on the water-bath, under reflux. The product, a heavy liquid, readily dissolved in acetone but no precipitate was obtained on adding ether. The acetone was evaporated off and a greenish mass was left behind. It was redissolved in acetone and crystallised.

It is a greenish compound, melting at 68° . It freely dissolves in acetone. On adding water decomposition takes place. (Found: Sb, 21.47; Br, 57.16. $[(C_2H_5)_3S]SbBr_4$ requires Sb, 21.36; Br, 57.03 per cent. Sulphur was found to be present qualitatively.)

Preparation of $[Et_3S]SbCl_3I$.—Antimony trichloride, ethyl sulphide and ethyl iodide in equimolecular proportion were gently warmed on the water-bath for a few minutes. The product of reaction, a viscous mass, was dissolved in acetone and precipitated by ether. The precipitate was dissolved in boiling acetone and crystallised in the usual way. It is a yellow shining crystalline substance, m.p. 156° . It is rather sparingly soluble in acetone and insoluble in other organic solvents. It is decomposed on adding excess of water. (Found: Sb, 25.71; Cl, 22.43, 22.41; I, 26.56; C, 14.92. $[(C_2H_5)_3S]SbCl_3I$ requires Sb, 25.68; Cl, 22.45; I, 26.79; C, 15.18 per cent.). When the reactants were heated for 2 to 3 hours, the whole mass turned tarry black. The tarry mass was dissolved in acetone and on the addition of ether, a yellow substance was precipitated. The precipitate was separated, dissolved in boiling acetone and a yellow crystalline substance was isolated in the usual way. It has the same melting point (156°) as the compound $[(C_2H_5)_3S]SbCl_3I$ and also identical physical and chemical properties. (Found: Sb, 25.88 per cent.).

The same compound was also obtained when $SbCl_3$ was treated with $(C_2H_5)_3SI$.

Preparation of $[Me_3S]SbCl_3I$.—Antimony trichloride, methyl sulphide and methyl iodide in about equimolecular proportions were warmed on the water-bath with a little acetone. Brilliant yellow crystals separated. These were separated and recrystallised from acetone in the usual way. It is a yellow crystalline substance, m.p. 189° . It is sparingly soluble in acetone. Its chemical properties are very similar to those of $[C_3H_5)_3S]SbCl_3I$. (Found: Sb, 27.98; Cl, 24.57; C, 29.22. $[(CH_3)_3]SbCl_3I$ requires Sb, 28.17; Cl, 24.63; C, 29.48 per cent.).

Preparation of $[Et_3S]_3SbBr_3I_3$.—Antimony tri-iodide was treated with ethyl sulphonium bromide in a large volume of acetone. A yellowish-red substance gradually separated but the contents were then warmed a little to ensure complete reaction. The precipitate was separated and crystallised from acetone.

It is a reddish-yellow substance, m.p. $182-83^{\circ}$. It is sparingly soluble in acetone and insoluble in other organic solvents. The

properties are similar to other compounds of the series. (Found: Sb, 10.93; total halide as AgBr and AgI, 0.2207 gm. from 0.2240 gm. of the substance. $[(C_2H_5)_3S]_3SbBr_3I_3$ requires Sb, 11.08; total halide, 0.2176 gm.

Conductivity of $[Et_3S]SbI_4$ in acetone at 27°.

Dilution (in litres).	Molecular conductivity.
570	126.7
1140	159.3
2280	205.6
4560	243.3
9120	279.8
18249	350.3

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Received March 18, 1931.

